

Efficient Use of Renewable Fertilisers

Livestock manure can be converted into **sustainable fertiliser** by using a biogas plant (anaerobic digestion) and microfiltration.

Mixed with water, the renewable fertiliser can be applied via fertigation. **Subsurface dripline irrigation systems** or **sprinklers** are used for this.

This innovation saves irrigation water and reduces the need for chemical fertilisers, minimising ammonia emissions and nitrate leaching.